

STUDIES IN INDIGOID DYES. PART XII. PHENANTHRA-THIOPHENE-INDIGOS

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Some thioindigoid dyes from 3-thiolphenanthrene and 2-thiolphenanthrene, similar to those obtained from 9-thiolphenanthrene (Dutta, *this Journal*, 1949, 28, 27), have been synthesised from the point of view of colour in relation to chemical constitution.

The syntheses of the thioindigoid dyes described in this paper involve the initial preparation of the hitherto unreported 2-thiolphenanthrene from pure potassium 2-phenanthrene sulphonate ("Organic Synthesis", Coll. Vol. 11, p. 482) by its conversion into sulphochloride and subsequent reduction. Corresponding to the derivatives of 3-thiolphenanthrene (Field, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1214) and 9-thiolphenanthrene (Dutta, *this Journal*, 1941, 18, 469) the derivatives of 2-thiolphenanthrene have been prepared. Part XI of this series of papers (Dutta, *this Journal*, 1949, 28, 27) dealt with the preparation and properties of thioindigoid dyes derived from 9-thiolphenanthrene and the present communication deals with similar dyes derived from 2- and 3-thiolphenanthrenes through their thioglycollic acids and their subsequent cyclisation to 2:1- and 3:4-phenanthra-2'-ketodihydrothiophenes (IV, III) corresponding to 9:10-phenanthra-2'-ketodihydrothiophene (V). Since, for the formation of a five membered ring in the cyclisation of β -3- and β -2-phenanthrylpropionic acids (Bachmann and Kloetzel, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 2207; Bergmann and Hillemann, *Ber.*, 1933, 66, 1302; Hillemann, *Ber.*, 1936, 69, 2610) ring-closure takes place in positions 4 and 1 respectively, it would appear that out of the two possibilities in the direction of the ring-closure, phenanthrene-3-and-2-thioglycollic acids would similarly cyclise at positions 4 and 1 respectively for the formation of a five membered ring and therefore they can be represented according to the following structures. The cyclisation of phenanthrene-9-thioglycollic acid (*loc. cit.*) at position 10 is in conformity with the accepted view of the greater reactivity of the 9:10-position of the phenanthrene ring.

The oxidation of the oxythiophene (III) by the usual procedure yielded the bis-compound (VI), whereas its condensation with phenanthraquinone, acenaphthaquinone and isatin produced the dyes (IX), (XII) and (XV) respectively.

Similar corresponding dyes have also been prepared from the oxythiophene (IV) and a comparison of the colour of the thioindigoid dyes, prepared from all the three isomeric phenanthra-2'-ketodihydrothiophene, is tabulated below.

TABLE I

P stands for phenanthrathiophene.

Compound.	Colour of crystals.	Colour of pyridine soln.	Colour of nitrobenzene soln.
(VI) <i>bis</i> -3:4-P-indigo	Dark violet	Violet	Dull violet
(VII) <i>bis</i> -2:1-P- "	Chocolate	Reddish brown	Reddish brown
(VIII) <i>bis</i> -9:10-P- "	Chocolate	Brown	Yellowish brown
(IX) 3:4-P-9-phenanthrene-indigo	Violet	Brownish violet	Purple
(X) 2:1-P- "	"	Brownish violet	Chocolate
(XI) 9:10-P- "	"	Chocolate	Chocolate
(XII) 3:4-P-2'-acenaphthylene-indigo	Dark violet	Brownish red	Purple
(XIII) 2:1-P- "	Purple	Purple	Purple
(XIV) 9:10-P- "	"	Red	Bright red
(XV) 3:4-P-3'-indol-indigo	Red	Orange-red	Red
(XVI) 2:1-P- "	Deep violet	Purple	Purple
(XVII) 9:10-P- "	Violet	Pinkish red	Red
	Deep red	Pinkish red	Purple

From a comparison of the colour of these isomeric phenanthrathiophene indigos it has been found that the 3:4-compounds are the deepest which was anticipated in accordance with the view of one of the authors (Dutta, *Ber.*, 1934, 67, 1319; 1935, 68, 1447; 1936, 69, 2343).

The dyes are lustrous and are very soluble in pyridine and nitrobenzene, moderately soluble in benzene and ethyl acetate and insoluble in alcohol. As they are found to be almost insoluble in alkaline hydrosulphite, a comparative study of the shades imparted by them on cotton could not be made. A study of the absorption spectra of these dyes will be communicated in a subsequent paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Phenanthrene-3-thioglycollic Acid.—Sodium carbonate solution (10%, 400 c.c.) containing 3-thiophenanthrene (8.2 g.) was heated on the water-bath with occasional shaking for about half an hour and the resulting turbid solution was filtered from a little undissolved oily residue, the filtrate treated with monochloroacetic acid (4 g.), previously neutralised with sodium carbonate solution, and further heated on the water-bath for an hour, cooled and filtered. Acidification of the filtrate with hydrochloric acid (Congo red) precipitated the thioglycollic acid as a white crystalline mass which was filtered, air-dried (9.5 g.) and crystallised from benzene in silky needles (8.7 g.), m.p. 146°. (Found: C, 71.55; H, 4.53. $C_{16}H_{12}O_2S$ requires C, 71.64; H, 4.47 per cent).

bis-3:4-Phenanthrathiophene-indigo (VI).—A mixture of the finely powdered and carefully dried phenanthrene-3-thioglycollic acid (5.36 g.), suspended in dry petroleum ether (b.p. 60°-80°, 50 c.c.), phosphorus pentachloride (4.2 g.) and three drops of pyridine as a catalyst was refluxed on the water-bath for about half an hour until everything went into solution, which, when thoroughly cooled in a freezing mixture, deposited the acid chloride as a clear oil at the bottom from which the clear supernatant liquid containing the phosphorus oxychloride was carefully decanted off. The oil was redissolved in petroleum ether (40 c.c.) and the solution treated with freshly prepared powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (5 g.) at the room temperature; the mixture was refluxed on the water-bath until the evolution of hydrochloric acid gas had ceased and gradually a dark red complex formed. After distilling off the petroleum ether the residue was decomposed with a mixture of crushed ice and hydrochloric acid (conc.), the resulting yellowish sticky mass of the thioindoxyl was extracted with ethyl acetate, washed once with dilute hydrochloric acid and thrice with water and the ethyl acetate distilled off. The yellow residue was extracted several times with warm dilute caustic soda solution (5%) and quickly filtered, as on standing the solution rapidly became green due to oxidation in air. On the addition of finely powdered potassium ferricyanide in excess to the alkaline filtrate the *bis*-indigo precipitated out as a reddish violet mass which was filtered off, washed with water and air-dried. It was purified by repeatedly extracting with hot ethyl acetate and the combined violet-red extract after filtration was concentrated, treated with petroleum ether and the precipitate so obtained was again dissolved in ethyl acetate, filtered and concentrated to a small bulk; on standing it gradually deposited the *bis*-compound as a dark violet, lustrous crystalline mass, which sintered at 207° and melted at 226°. (Found: C, 77.23; H, 3.31. $C_{22}H_{16}O_2S_2$ requires C, 77.42; H, 3.32 per cent).

As the oxythiophene was readily oxidised in air its purification was found to be extremely difficult and as such it was immediately condensed with the various diketones as noted below.

3:4-Phenanthrathiophene-g'-phenanthrene-indigo (IX).—Phenanthraquinone (0.5 g.) dissolved in acetic acid (30 c.c.) was added to the filtered solution of 3:4-phenanthra-2'-ketodihydrothiophene (0.6 g.) in acetic acid (25 c.c.) and the mixture heated for ten minutes with the addition of hydrochloric acid (1 c.c., d 1.19) when a dark precipitate immediately separated out which was filtered, washed with a little acetic acid and finally with alcohol. The residue after digestion with boiling alcohol was filtered and repeatedly extracted with hot benzene, and the combined extracts concentrated to a small volume; on standing it gradually deposited the thioindigo as a dark chocolate, lustrous, crystalline mass sintering at 204°, m.p. 245°. (Found: C, 81.75; H, 3.78. $C_{26}H_{16}O_2S$ requires C, 81.82; H, 3.63 per cent).

3:4-Phenanthrathiophene-2'-acenaphthylene-indigo (XII) was prepared in the same way as the previous compound from acenaphthaquinone (0.45 g.) and 3:4-phenanthra-2'-ketodihydrothiophene (0.6 g.) in acetic acid solution with traces of hydrochloric acid, and purified in the same way. The concentrated benzene solution on slow evaporation at room temperature yielded a dark shining crystalline mass, decomposing at 254°. (Found: C, 80.96; H, 3.48. $C_{22}H_{14}O_2S$ requires C, 81.15; H, 3.38 per cent).

3:4-Phenanthrathiophene-3'-indol-indigo (XV) was obtained as the previous compounds by condensing the 3:4-phenanthra-2'-ketodihydrothiophene (0.6 g.) and isatin (0.4 g.) in acetic acid in presence of traces of hydrochloric acid. The indigo was purified from hot benzene like the previous compounds and obtained as a dark crystalline mass, m.p. 230° with previous sintering at 212°. (Found: C, 75.81; H, 3.52. $C_{24}H_{12}O_2NS$ requires C, 75.99; H, 3.43 per cent).

2-Thiolphenanthrene (I, R = H)

A mixture of pure potassium 2-phenanthrene sulphonate (purity determined by preparing the *p*-toluidine salt) (40 g.) and phosphorus pentachloride (50 g.) was treated with phosphorus oxychloride (10 c.c.) and heated in an oil-bath at 140° under reflux for one hour. After distilling off the oxychloride (bath temperature, 140°-160°), the semisolid residue was treated with crushed ice and left overnight. The sulphochloride, obtained as a white solid, was filtered, thoroughly washed with water, mixed with zinc dust (160 g.) and to the mixture sulphuric acid (240 c.c. diluted with 720 c.c. of water) was gradually added. When the reaction had slackened at room temperature, the mixture was refluxed for 3 hours with frequent shaking, cooled, filtered and

the residue after washing with water was extracted repeatedly with hot ether, and the combined extract was dried over fused calcium chloride. Evaporation of the ether left the 2-thiol compound as a yellowish white crystalline solid (17 g.) which, when distilled in vacuum, yielded the pure compound (b.p. $228^{\circ}/0.1$ mm.) as white glistening plates (14 g.). Crystallisation from petroleum ether (b.p. 60° - 80°) gave the very pure compound in shining white plates, m.p. 112 - 13° , yield 12 g. It became yellowish on keeping. (Found : S, 15.19. $C_{14}H_{10}S$ requires S, 15.24 per cent).

Phenanthrene-2-disulphide (II).—An alcoholic solution of iodine in slight excess when added to a solution of 2-thiolphenanthrene (0.5 g.) in alcohol (50 c.c.) immediately separated yellowish white crystals. To ensure completion of the reaction, the mixture was refluxed on the water-bath for half an hour, cooled, the crystals filtered and recrystallised from benzene in colorless needles, m.p. 177° . (Found : S, 15.28. $C_{16}H_{10}S_2$ requires S, 15.31 per cent).

2-Acetylthiolphenanthrene (I, R = COMe).—A mixture of 2-thiolphenanthrene (0.5 g.) and acetyl chloride (1.5 c.c.) was refluxed on a water-bath for 2 hours when an almost colorless solution was obtained. The reaction mixture on cooling solidified to a crystalline mass which was allowed to stand overnight in contact with water; the crystals were filtered off and washed with dilute caustic soda solution, followed by water. Recrystallisation from alcohol yielded the pure product in beautiful colorless, felted needles, m.p. 121° . (Found : S, 12.56. $C_{16}H_{12}OS$ requires S, 12.7 per cent).

2-Benzoylthiolphenanthrene (I, R = COPh).—2-Thiolphenanthrene (0.5 g.) was heated with benzoyl chloride (1.5 c.c.) in an oil-bath at 150° - 160° for 3 hours and the slightly coloured reaction mixture on cooling solidified to a thick paste, which was allowed to stand in water overnight. The solid residue after filtration was recrystallised from a large volume of alcohol in clusters of colorless needles, m.p. 151° . (Found : S, 9.96. $C_{21}H_{14}OS$ requires S, 10.19 per cent).

2-Methylthiolphenanthrene (I, R = Me).—The vigorous reaction of 2-thiolphenanthrene with methyl sulphate in alkaline solution (cf. 9-methylthiolphenanthrene, *loc. cit.*) gave a product which could not be crystallised. Hence the following method was adopted for its successful preparation.

2-Thiolphenanthrene (0.5 g.), dissolved in anhydrous acetone (30 c.c.), was heated with excess of anhydrous potassium carbonate and methyl iodide (1.5 c.c.) under an efficient reflux for 2 hours. The solution after filtering off the potassium carbonate was evaporated to dryness when a slightly coloured solid residue was left behind. Repeated crystallisation from alcohol yielded the pure product as colorless rosettes of needles, m.p. 126° . (Found : S, 13.93. $C_{15}H_{12}S$ requires S, 14.28 per cent).

Phenanthrene-2-thioglycollic Acid.—2-Thiolphenanthrene (8.2 g.) was prepared in a manner similar to phenanthrene-3-thioglycollic acid. The sodium salt of the thioglycollic acid, unlike its other isomers, which are soluble, immediately solidified to a white crystalline mass. After heating for half an hour the reaction mixture was cooled, thoroughly agitated with hydrochloric acid until acidic (Congo red) and allowed to stand overnight. The thioglycollic acid was filtered, washed with a little water and after drying recrystallised from benzene in small rosettes of needles, m.p. 162° , yield 9 g. (Found : C, 71.51; H, 4.57. $C_{16}H_{12}O_2S$ requires C, 71.64; H, 4.47 per cent).

bis-2:1-Phenanthrathiophene-indigo (VII) was prepared in a similar way as 3:4-isomer (*vide supra*) from pure dry phenanthrene-2-thioglycollic acid (2.68 g.), as a chocolate mass having a metallic lustre. The filtered precipitate was washed thoroughly with water, digested with boiling alcohol in which it was almost insoluble and filtered. The air-dried residue was then dissolved in benzene, filtered from a little insoluble matter, the filtrate concentrated to a small bulk which on slow evaporation at room temperature deposited the *bis*-compound as a shining chocolate crystalline mass, m.p. 197-98°. (Found: C, 77.19; H, 3.28. $C_{22}H_{14}O_2S_2$ requires C, 77.42; H, 3.22 per cent).

2: 1-Phenanthra-2'-ketodihydrothiophene rapidly underwent oxidation in air and as such like its 3: 4-isomer it was immediately condensed with various *o*-diketones given below.

2: 1-Phenanthrathiophene-9'-phenanthrene-indigo (X).—Phenanthraquinone (0.52 g.), dissolved in hot glacial acetic acid (30 c.c.), was mixed with the filtered solution of 2: 1-phenanthra-2'-ketodihydrothiophene (0.72 g.) in glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) and refluxed for ten minutes with the addition of a little hydrochloric acid when a dark chocolate precipitate separated out. The filtered residue was thoroughly washed with glacial acetic acid followed by alcohol, and after digestion with boiling alcohol in which it was almost insoluble, it was dissolved in boiling benzene and filtered. The filtrate on concentration to a thick syrup deposited the dye as a brownish violet crystalline mass, sintering at 218°, m. p. 258°. (Found: C, 81.63; H, 3.71. $C_{20}H_{10}O_2S$ requires C, 81.82; H, 3.63 per cent).

2: 1-Phenanthrathiophene-2'-acenaphthylene-indigo (XIII) was prepared in the same way as the previous compound by condensing acenaphthaquinone (0.45 g.) with 2: 1-phenanthra-2'-ketodihydrothiophene (0.6 g.) in acetic acid solution in presence of hydrochloric acid. It was purified as the foregoing compound and was obtained as a purple crystalline mass, m.p. above 290°. (Found: C, 80.83; H, 3.41. $C_{22}H_{14}O_2S$ requires C, 81.15; H, 3.38 per cent).

2: 1-Phenanthrathiophene-3'-indol-indigo was obtained as the above compounds from 2: 1-phenanthra-2'-ketodihydrothiophene (0.62 g.) and isatin (0.37 g.). It was crystallised from nitrobenzene in lustrous violet needles, m.p. above 290°. (Found: C, 75.83; H, 3.48. $C_{24}H_{16}O_2NS$ requires C, 75.99; H, 3.43 per cent).